

Original Research

***In vitro* conservation and multiplication of *Cymbidium finlaysonianum* Lindl. - A horticulturally important floriferous orchid species**

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Abstract

The study is envisioned to assist *ex situ* conservation of horticulturally important endangered epiphytic orchid species, *Cymbidium finlaysonianum*. The *in vitro* cultures were initiated through an asymbiotic seed germination technique, using undehisced capsules, in Murashige and Skoog (1962) medium and its combinations with auxin (α -naphthalene acetic acid; NAA 1 mg l⁻¹) and cytokinin (6-benzylamino purine; BAP 1 mg l⁻¹). MS medium (control), favoured early initiation of germination in the seeds. Attempts were also made to multiply protocorms in basal medium. Although growth regulators favoured protocorm multiplication, they also multiplied in Basal MS medium. Synergistic action of NAA and BAP was observed in seedling development, similar to that of the basal medium. Seedlings were formed after 20 weeks.

Keywords

Cymbidium; epiphyte, seed germination, organic growth supplements

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In vitro ohranjanje in razmnoževanje *Cymbidium finlaysonianum* Lindl. – vrtnarsko pomembna cvetoča vrsta orhideje

Izvleček

Študija naj bi pomagala pri ohranjanju ogrožene epifitske vrste orhideje *Cymbidium finlaysonianum*, ki je pomembna za vrtnarstvo, *ex situ*. *In vitro* kulture so bile začete s tehniko asimbiotičnega kaljenja semen, z uporabo nedeljenih plodov, v gojišču Murashige in Skoog (1962) in njegovih kombinacijah z auksinom (α -naftalenocetna kislina; NAA 1 mg l⁻¹) in citokinini (6-benzilaminopurin; BAP 1 mg l⁻¹). MS medij (kontrola) je spodbudil zgodnje začetno kaljenje semen. Poskušali so tudi pomnožiti protokorm v bazalnem mediju. Čeprav so rastni regulatorji spodbujali pomnoževanje protokormov, so se ti pomnožili tudi v bazalnem MS mediju. Pri razvoju sadik je bilo opazno sinergistično delovanje NAA in BAP, podobno kot v bazalnem mediju. Sadike so se oblikovale po 20 tednih.

Ključne besede

Cymbidium; epifit, kalitev semen, ekološki dodatki za rast

Introduction

The plants are indispensable for the precise functioning of an ecosystem. Swift plant biodiversity loss across the globe, due to the extermination of the forests, has raised concerns regarding the threat to human life. The environmentalists and conservationists have emphasised the importance of habitat conservation. Each plant species' survival is of utmost importance. Since many plant species have become extinct or endangered, orchids are no exception (CITES, 2024).

In nature, the orchids are one of the most magnificent congregations of flowering plants, found ubiquitously from the tropics to the higher elevations. Orchid blooms are quite diverse in terms of size, colour, and structure. Besides being floriferously important, the orchids act as essential ecological indicators in addition to serving medicinal purposes (Joshi et al., 2009; Kaur, 2021).

Orchids are economically and commercially significant flowering plants. They belong to the extremely advanced monocot angiosperm family Orchidaceae, which embraces 22,000-31,000 species approximately and covers 7.2% of the flowering plants in India (Antony et al., 2014). Orchid flowers possess an unexpectedly high commercial value both domestically and abroad in the floriculture industry, owing to their gorgeous, colourful, scented blossoms, with long vase life. Diverse orchids are grown for financial advantages, primarily in the floricultural business. While orchids are often cultivated for their decorative value,

they are also used across the world as food, natural cures, and other significant cultural objects (Kasulo et al., 2009; Khasim and Rao, 1999). Being highly versatile, the orchids have been collected unabatedly from their natural habitats; hence, they have become rare and are included in Appendix I and II among other rare plant species by CITES (2024). Thus, in order to conserve their gene pool presently, one of the species of *Cymbidium finlaysonianum* has been selected for mass propagation under *in vitro* conditions using an asymbiotic seed germination technique.

Cymbidiums are one of the most popular orchids in horticulture, marketed as cut-flowers, buttonholes and as pot plants, producing many large and long-lasting flowers. The genus *Cymbidium* currently comprises nearly 52 species distributed throughout South and Eastern Asia, the Malay Archipelago and north and east Australia (Puy and Cribb, 2007). *C. finlaysonianum* Lindl. It is an epiphytic, sympodial, herbaceous orchid species that grows up to 90 cm tall, forming dense and wide tufts with close conical to ovoid pseudobulbs covered by the foliar bases. The plant bears flowers that are arranged in a pendulous racemose inflorescence, hanging from the base of the pseudobulb, 0.3 - 1.3 m long and carrying numerous small yellow and red fragrant flowers with a diameter of 5 - 6 cm (Opchat, 2000). Presently, efforts have been made to conserve the germplasm of *C. finlaysonianum* through an asymbiotic seed germination technique and multiplying without the use of PGRs in the nutrient pool.

Materials and Methods

Plant material

The capsules of *Cymbidium finlaysonianum* were collected from naturally pollinated plants growing on the trunk of *Artocarpus heterophyllus* (jackfruit tree) in the natural habitat of Chandranathpur, Assam, India (latitudinal range: 24°58'00.5"N, longitudinal range: 92°42'09.0"E). Seeds from undehisced capsules of *C. finlaysonianum* were used to initiate cultures in vitro (Fig. 1A-C).

Culture medium and surface sterilisation of the capsule

Defined asymbiotic orchid seed germination medium, such as Murashige and Skoog (1962) MS medium (Hi-media, Mumbai, India) was used to initiate the cultures. The pH of the medium was adjusted to 5.7 using 1 N HCl / 1 N NaOH before autoclaving. The medium was gelled with agar (Hi-media, Mumbai, India), dispensed into (25 × 150 mm) test tubes and autoclaved at 121°C at a pressure of 1.06 kg cm⁻² for 15 min. Autoclaved medium was kept at 37°C for 2–3 days to check for any contamination. Seed viability was performed by using the TTC salt (2,3,5-triphenyl-2H-tetrazolium chloride; 1%; pH 6.5) staining method. The seeds were kept in the dark while immersed in stain for eight hours at 30°C.

The capsules were first gently scrubbed with an ultra-soft brush in running tap water to remove any debris from their surface. Each capsule was rinsed thoroughly with dishwashing detergent solution. The capsule was swabbed with ethyl alcohol in a laminar air flow hood and sequentially disinfected with an aqueous solution of 0.05% mercuric chloride (Qualigens, Mumbai, India) containing 1–2 drops of “Teepol” for 2–3 minutes and 0.05% streptomycin (Angel Pharma International, India) treatment for

1-2 minutes. Finally, the capsule was rinsed thoroughly with sterilised distilled water. Thereafter, the capsule was incised longitudinally, and the seeds were scooped out into a Petri dish.

Inoculations and incubation

The culture vessels, inoculated with seeds, were incubated under a 12-h photoperiod under 40 μmol m⁻² s⁻¹ light intensity (fluorescent tubes, Philips India Ltd, Mumbai, India) at approximately 25 ± 2°C temperature. The cultures were sub-cultured into their respective fresh medium as and when required.

Observations and data analysis

After 4 weeks of inoculation, a few seeds were taken out of the culture vessel with the help of a spatula. They were placed in a drop of water on a glass slide and observed under a microscope. Once the embryos emerged from the seed coat and spherules were formed, the observations were taken at 1-week intervals. Different development events of germinating seeds were observed (Table 1), and photographs were taken using a stereozoom microscope (Nikon, H600L, Japan). Calculations of seed germination were done by the formula (Kaur and Bhutani, 2014). The cultures were observed regularly under a binocular microscope (Olympus SZX10, Japan), and morphological events were recorded. Eight replicates were used per treatment. To check the reproducibility of the protocol, the experiment was repeated twice. The experiment followed a completely randomised design. The results were tested using a one-way ANOVA test and were analysed using the Tukey Multiple Comparison using SPSS (version 17) software package (SPSS Inc., Chicago, USA). The reproducibility of the protocol was checked by repeating the experiment.

Table 1. Evaluation of morphological events of seeds of *Cymbidium finlaysonianum*.

Tabela 1. Ocena morfoloških pojavov semen *Cymbidium finlaysonianum*.

Event	Sequential morphological event
1 st event	Imbibed seed, swollen, still covered or partially covered by testa (=viable seed)
2 nd event	Enlarged seed without testa (=germination)
3 rd event	Protocorms with rhizoids
4 th event	Protocorms with a pointed shoot apex and rhizoids (appearance of shoot apex)
5 th event	Seedlings with one or more leaves (emergence of the first leaf)
6 th event	Enlargement of leaves (2-3 leaves) and the emergence of the first root

Histochemical studies

The modified seed viability technique established by Terry et al. (2003) was employed to evaluate the seed vitality using the Tetrazolium test (Alvarez-Pardo et al., 2006). The seeds were washed several times with distilled water after initially being soaked in 1% (v/v) Tween 80 for 20 minutes. For 24 hours, the seeds were suspended in distilled water. Seeds were then put in 1% (w/v) solution of 2,3,5-triphenyl tetrazolium chloride (TTC) in a beaker after the water had been discarded. The reaction was left to run for 24 hours at 30°C in the dark. The seeds were inspected under a stereomicroscope (Olympus SXZ12, Japan) after being rinsed once with distilled water to eliminate excess stain after discarding the TTC solution. Seeds were scored as viable if the embryo was stained red or orange and as non-viable if the embryo was unstained.

Histological studies

For the purpose of tracking the origin of secondary protocorms (*neo-formations*) during protocorm multiplication, hand sections of a clump of multiplying protocorms were gently and carefully inserted into potato pith. Thin slices or sections were selected to prepare temporary slides by staining them with safranin stain. The slides were observed under a stereoscopic microscope (Nikon Digital Sight, DS, R11 Nikon Corporation, Japan).

Results

In the present experiment, the ability of basal MS medium and its combinations with plant growth regulators (PGRs) (auxins and cytokinin) was tested on seed germination percentage, onset of seed germination and subsequent morphogenetic changes associated with seedling development. The germination frequency varied with the kind of PGR treatment. Morphogenetic milestones observed from the germination of the seed to the development of the seedling are summarised (Tables 2-4) and illustrated (Figures 1-4).

The capsule, from where the scooped-out seeds germinated readily, was measured 10.9 ± 0.28 cm in length and 2.81 ± 0.09 cm in width (Table 2, Figure 1a and 1b). The seeds were highly reduced, creamish-white in colour, powdery or dust-like in texture and innumerable. (Figure 1c).

The seeds were embryonate and viable. To ensure viability in the seeds, the TTC test showed that the embryos

stained red and consisted of undifferentiated cells enclosed within a hyaline seed coat (Figure 1d). The germination of seeds was not obligatory to the use of PGRs, as the seeds efficiently germinated on basal medium, i.e. on MS medium (Figure 2). The seeds (Figure 3a) began germination within 3.80 ± 0.09 weeks of culture on MS basal (control) medium, with the swelling of the embryo (Figure 3a). These swollen seeds emerged as a spherule by piercing through the hyaline seed coat, as evident by the successive stages (Figure 3c-e). The spherule grew in size lengthwise while remaining attached to the seed coat and developed absorbing hair primordia (Figure 3f), developed chlorophyll and absorbing hairs at the base in a 7.10 ± 0.11 weeks old culture (Figure 3g). A close observation indicated that the later lower portion of the spherule developed more absorbing hair (Figure 3a). The spherules further grew to form a pear-shaped protocorm (Figure 3h) with absorbing hairs all around the lower portion of the protocorm in 9.30 ± 0.23 weeks. At the initial stages of protocorm formation, a shoot primordial initial (1st leaf primordia) was evident at the upper end in 13.05 ± 0.3 weeks, and later dense rhizoidal growth was observed all around at the basal portion of the protocorm (Figure 3i). Successively, another leaf primordia and root primordia were formed after 15.55 ± 0.05 weeks and 18.4 ± 0.14 weeks, respectively (Table 3). Seedlings, complete with 2-3 leaves and 1-2 roots, were developed after 20 weeks.

NAA, in the culture medium, also favoured cent per cent germination but delayed all sequential morphogenetic processes, even arresting differentiation of the protocorms and delaying chlorophyll development (Figures 3j and 3k). These protocorms were shifted to half-strength MS medium supplemented with NAA (1 mg L⁻¹) and peptone (1mg l⁻¹). Replacement of NAA with BAP also showed a similar effect, except it favoured multiplication of the protocorms (Figure 3i). A combination of auxin and cytokinin proved synergistic in action as the seeds germinated within 4.2 ± 0.07 weeks (Figure 2). The protocorms multiplied profusely (Figure 3m) and formed seedlings in 20.35 ± 0.19 weeks (Figure 3n, Table 3). The growth of spherules remained arrested in both MS + NAA (1mg l⁻¹) and MS + BAP (1mg l⁻¹), which was resumed upon a shift to ½ strength MS medium supplemented with NAA and peptone at (1 g l⁻¹). The shoots rooted after 25 weeks (Table 4).

Interestingly, the protocorms multiplied profusely in MS alone and supplemented with BAP + NAA (Figure 4a and 4b). The protocorms multiplied at the base of the seedlings (Figure 4c). Histological hand sections indicated the inherent polyembryonic potential of the protocorms (Figure 4d and 4e)

Table 2. Morphological features of *Cymbidium finlaysonianum* capsules at different stages of development.Tabela 2. Morfološke značilnosti kapsul *Cymbidium finlaysonianum* v različnih fazah razvoja.

Characteristics	Specifications	
	Immature	Mature
Capsule Colour	Green	Yellowish-green
Seed colour	Whitish- yellow	Pale-yellow
Capsule length (cm)	10.7 ± 0.18	10.9 ± 0.28
Capsule width (cm)	1.48 ± 0.24	2.81 ± 0.09
Capsule surface	Smooth, depressed ridges	Rough, prominent ridges

Data represents Mean ± Standard error

Figure 1. *Cymbidium finlaysonianum*. (a) Yellow-green undeveloped capsule measured lengthwise, (b) Capsule measured widthwise, (c) Minute dust-like seeds, (d) Viable seeds with their embryo stained red upon treatment with TTC solution (10x).

Slika 1. *Cymbidium finlaysonianum*. (a) Rumeno-zelena nepreklopljena kapsula, merjena po dolžini, (b) kapsula, merjena po širini, (c) drobna semena, podobna prahu, (d) vitalna semena z zarodkom, obarvanim rdeče po obdelavi z raztopino TTC (10x).

Fig. 2 Time taken by the seeds to germinate in MS medium and its combination with growth adjuncts.

Figure 2. Represents the time taken in weeks by the seeds germinating in MS medium and its combination with growth adjuncts.

Slika 2. Predstavlja čas v tednih, ki ga potrebujejo semena za kalitev v MS-mediju in njegovi kombinaciji z dodatki za rast.

Figure 3. *In vitro* asymbiotic seed germination and seedling development of *Cymbidium finlaysonianum* in MS medium. (a) Embryonate seed with seed coat intact (10x), (b) Swelling of the embryos (10x), (c), (d) swollen seed emerging as spherule by piercing through the hyaline seed coat, (e) formation of absorbing hairs at the basal portion of the embryo (40x), (f) embryo attached to the seed coat at one point (40x), (g) globular spherule with multicellular trichomes arising from one end of the spherule (40x), (h) pear-shaped protocorm with hairs attached to its basal surface (40x), (i) Formation of 1st leaf primordium in protocorm and more rhizoids at the basal portion of the protocorm (20x), (j) Achlorophyllous spherules in MS + NAA (1mg l⁻¹), (k) Cultures treated in MS media + NAA (1 mg l⁻¹) after 12 weeks of inoculations showing initiation of development of chlorophyll, (l) Protocorm development in basal MS medium after 12 weeks, (m) Development of protocorms after 8.4 weeks of inoculation in MS + BAP (1 mg l⁻¹), (n) Seedling formation in MS + BAP (1 mg l⁻¹) + NAA (1 mg l⁻¹) (20x).

Slika 3. *In vitro* asimbiotično kaljenje semen in razvoj sadik *Cymbidium finlaysonianum* v MS mediju. (a) Zarodno seme z nepoškodovano semensko lupino (10x), (b) nabrekanje zarodkov (10x), (c), (d) nabrekano seme, ki se pojavi kot krogla, ko prebije hialinsko semensko lupino, (e) nastanek absorpcijskih dlačic na bazalnem delu zarodka (40x), (f) zarodek, pritrjen na semensko lupino na eni točki (40x), (g) kroglasta kroglasta oblika z večceličnimi trichomi, ki izhajajo iz enega konca kroglaste oblike (40x), (h) hruškasta protocorm z dlačicami, pritrjenimi na njeno bazalno površino (40x), (i) Oblikovanje prvega listnega primordija v protokormu in več rizoidov na bazalnem delu protokorma (20x), (j) Achlorofilne krogle v MS + NAA (1mg l⁻¹), (k) Kulture, obdelane v MS mediju + NAA (1 mg l⁻¹) po 12 tednih inokulacij, ki kažejo začetek razvoja klorofila, (l) Razvoj protokorma v bazalnem MS mediju po 12 tednih, (m) Razvoj protokormov po 8,4 tednih inokulacije v MS + BAP (1 mg l⁻¹), (n) Oblikovanje sadik v MS + BAP (1 mg l⁻¹) + NAA (1 mg l⁻¹) (20x).

Table 3. *In vitro* asymbiotic seed germination in *Cymbidium finlaysonianum* and associated morphogenetic events in MS medium and its combinations with growth adjuncts.

Tabela 3. *In vitro* asimbiotično kaljenje semen *Cymbidium finlaysonianum* in povezani morfogogenetski dogodki v MS mediju in njegovih kombinacijah z dodatki za rast.

Additive	Germination (%)	Time Taken for (wks)					
		Development of			Differentiation of		Development of
		Spherule	Chlorophyll	Protocorm	First leaf	First root	
Control	100.00±0.00 ^a	5.45 ± 0.28 ^a	7.10 ± 0.11 ^b	9.30 ± 0.23 ^a	13.05±0.30 ^b	18.4 ± 0.14 ^b	20.00 ± 0.20 ^a
BAP	90.01±0.00 ^b	6.60 ± 0.38 ^b	7.35 ± 0.17 ^b	10.8 ± 0.46 ^b	Cultures shifted to ½ MS + BAP +P		
NAA	100.0±0.00 ^a	8.35 ± 0.05 ^c	12.57 ± 0.12 ^c	15.8 ± 0.69 ^c	Cultures shifted to ½ MS + NAA +P		
BAP+NAA	85.0.00±0.00 ^c	9.34 ± 0.04 ^c	6.12 ± 0.15 ^a	8.40 ± 0.12 ^a	9.80 ± 0.46 ^a	17.42 ± 0.09 ^a	20.35 ± 0.19 ^a

MS medium, Murashige and Skoog (1962) medium; Concentration of growth regulators, 1mg l⁻¹. Values in a column with the same superscripts are not significantly different at p ≤ 0.05

Table 4. Shows *in vitro* morphogenetic changes in germinating entities upon a shift to ½ MS medium.

Tabela 4. Prikazuje *in vitro* morfogogenetske spremembe v kalivih entitetah ob spremembi v ½ MS mediju.

Additives	Time Taken in (wks)		
	Differentiation of		Development of
	First leaf	First Root	
½ MS+BAP + P	13.05 ± 0.30	19.40 ± 0.14	25.00 ± 0.20
½ MS+NAA + P	17.22 ± 0.15	22.35 ± 0.19	25.00 ± 0.12

MS medium, Murashige and Skoog (1962) medium; Concentration of growth regulators = 1 mg l⁻¹, Peptone (P) = 1 mg l⁻¹; Data represents mean ± SD.

Figure 4. *In vitro* asymbiotic seed germination and seedling development of *Cymbidium finlaysonianum* in MS medium. (a) Multiplication of protocorms in MS medium basal (20x), (b) Multiplication of protocorms in MS medium + BAP + NAA (20x), (c) Protocorms multiplication at the base of shoots in MS + BAP (1 mg l⁻¹) + NAA (1 mg l⁻¹) (20x), (d-e) Histological hand sections indicating multiplication of the protocorms in MS + BAP (1 mg l⁻¹) + NAA (1 mg l⁻¹) (20x).

Slika 4. *In vitro* asimbiotično kaljenje semen in razvoj sadik *Cymbidium finlaysonianum* v MS mediju. (a) Razmnoževanje protocormov v MS mediju basal (20x), (b) Razmnoževanje protocormov v MS mediju + BAP + NAA (20x), (c) Razmnoževanje protocormov na dnu poganjkov v MS + BAP (1 mg l⁻¹) + NAA (1 mg l⁻¹) (20x), (d-e) Histoški ročni prerezi, ki kažejo razmnoževanje protocormov v MS + BAP (1 mg l⁻¹) + NAA (1 mg l⁻¹) (20x).

Discussion

Utilising *in vitro* methods aids in protecting the genetic material of vulnerable species. *In vitro* asymbiotic seed germination is helpful in conserving orchid species, since it reduces the time gap between pollination and seed germination (Sagawa, 1963). Additionally, tissue culture is extensively utilised in genetic transformation investigations and can be utilised to clone apomictic taxa and propagate desirable genotypes (Sagawa, 1963). In this study, seed germination of *C. finlaysonianum* was influenced by the maturity level of the capsule and growth regulators in the medium. The efficacy of Murashige and Skoog (1962) medium was tested, along with checking the germination potential of *C. finlaysonianum* seeds in basal MS medium and its combinations with PGRs. Literature survey indicates that PGRs such as auxins and cytokinins [2,4-dichlorophenoxy acetic acid (2,4-D); naphthalene acetic acid (NAA), 6-benzylaminopurine (BAP)], and synthetic phenylurea derivatives (PBU, 4-CPPU, and 2,3-MDPU) are considered as the agents, that are responsible for developing genetic variability in the cultures (Sales and Butardo, 2014; Sun et al., 2013). In crops like orchid, which is floriculturally and commercially very important, and genetic uniformity is desired, the *in vitro* cultures should avoid the use of PGRs as they increase the chances of occurrence of genetic variations. Currently, seed germination does not require the addition of PGRs, and these germinated successfully in basal medium (control), indicating that there was already a sufficient level of endogenous hormones available in the seeds themselves that initiated germination in the seeds. Moreover, the nutritional requirements of orchid seeds, in terms of type and quantity, can vary at various developmental stages in the cultures (Arditti and Ernst, 1984). A similar kind of response of seed germination in basal medium is also recorded in *Coelogyne flaccida* (Kaur and Bhutani, 2014) and *Vanda testacea* (Kaur, 2021).

Our experiment strongly indicates that the use of PGRs can be successfully avoided, as the seeds of *C. finlaysonianum* germinated with 100% frequency in the control (MS basal). Whereas previous studies show that in different media such as Knudson C medium (KC), New Dogashima medium (ND), and Vacin and Went medium (VW) (Rittirat et al., 2018), the seeds germinated with a maximum of 98 per cent frequency in Knudson C (Knudson, 1946) medium and Hyponex leaf fertiliser (HS) media (Rittirat et al., 2018). The germination of *C. finlaysonianum* seeds in different

media indicates their wide nutritional amplitude and simple nutritional requirements.

Plant tissue culture is a very efficient technique for clonal propagation; however, the resulting regenerants often show a number of somaclonal variations. A survey of literature indicates that plant growth regulators (PGRs), individually or in combinations, can behave as mutagens (D'Amato and Bayliss, 1985). A perusal of literature reveals that the size of orchid seed is quite small, about 0.25 to 1.2 mm (length) and 0.09 to 1.2 mm (width), and a single capsule contains about 4 million powdery seeds (Arditti, 1967), and the present species is no exception. The success of *in vitro* asymbiotic seed germination largely depends upon the capsule's maturity stage at the time of harvesting. This has been confirmed through the current study and earlier studies made in *C. flaccida* (Kaur and Bhutani, 2014). Earlier, a similar kind of response was achieved in *Cephalanthera falcata*, in which seeds harvested at a very early stage germinated with poor frequency (Yamazaki and Miyoshi, 2006). In our cultures, this kind of germination response could be attributed to a less developed embryo, as earlier also suggested by Yamazaki and Miyoshi (2006) in *Cephalanthera falcata*.

Presently, 100% response of the seed procured from 18-week-old cultures was achieved due to the metabolically awakened, well-developed embryos. The result is similar to the earlier findings in *Dendrobium chrysotoxum* (Kaur and Bhutani, 2011), *Paphiopedilum Venustum* (Kaur and Bhutani, 2014), and *Vanda testacea* (Kaur, 2021). Our results are in accord with earlier reports in *Cleisostoma ramaciferum* (Temjensangba and Deb, 2006) and in *Vanda*, where very young and mature capsules failed to germinate or resulted in a decreased germination frequency (Sharma, 1998). Earlier reports in *Phalaenopsis amabilis* var. *formosa* (Lee and Philips, 2008) and *Dendrobium nobile* (Vasudevan and van Staden, 2010) indicate the existence of a correlation between the internal organisation of immature seeds and their germinating abilities.

Cytokinin (BAP 1mg^l⁻¹) also showed a similar kind of response as that of the control in seed germination. Literature studies reveal that cytokinins are extremely important growth regulators that affect seed germination *in vitro* (Harvais, 1982). They are incorporated extensively in *in vitro* orchid seed germination medium (Arditti and Ernst, 1993). Orchid seeds contain a meagre amount of reserve nutrients as lipid droplets (Arditti and Ernst, 1984), and cytokinin assists the seeds in utilising these complex carbohydrates, without which germination could not be accomplished (De

Pauw et al.,1995).

The initiation of multiple meristematic zones composed of densely packed meristematic cells, forming new meristemoids, is already on record (Young et al., 2000; Ziv et al.,1998). The cells with dense cytoplasm and conspicuous nuclei were involved in the formation of globular bodies, which is an important characteristic feature of the embryogenic cells as earlier studied in species belonging to *Lycium barbarum* (Li et al., 2001), *Malaxis acuminata* (Kaur and Bhutani, 2010), *Dendrobium chrysotoxum* (Kaur, 2017). These globules gradually grew in size, having no vascular connections with the surrounding peripheral tissues and eventually transformed into secondary protocorms (PLBs). The PLBs proliferated further to produce secondary PLBs as reported earlier (Kaur, 2017; Zhao et al., 2008), assisted with the germplasm multiplication and conservation *in vitro*. NAA delayed morphogenetic events, but in combination with BAP proved slightly effective. A similar kind of response of NAA was earlier observed in *Vanda dearie* (Jualang et al., 2014), where NAA treatment delayed seed germination and induced necrosis in protocorm development.

Conclusion

The present experiment is a one-step protocol for *in vitro* conservation of *C. finlaysonianum* and concludes that *C. finlaysonianum* has very simple nutritional requirements for seed germination. Cent of seeds can be germinated without the inclusion of PGRs. The basal medium proved to be promising for the initiation of seed germination, multipli-

cation of the protocorms, and also supported the growth of the cultures. This simple protocol can certainly contribute to the conservation of this floriculturally important orchid species. Further experimental studies are directed to check the genetic fidelity of the regenerants and to acclimatise seedlings that are raised *in vitro*, thus restoring them to their natural habitat.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization, K.S.; methodology, K.S.and J.M.; validation, K.S.; formal analysis, K.S.and J.M.; investigation, K.S.; resources, K.S.; data curation, K.S.; writing—original draft preparation, K.S.; writing—review, and editing,; supervision, K.S.; All authors have read, and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Data Availability

Research data is deposited at Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18239738>)

Conflicts of Interest

There is no potential conflict of interest shown by authors.

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